

Study of the Blue Perchromate prepared in presence of Tartaric Acid*

B. S. Rajput† and R. C. Rai

The blue perchromate has been prepared in presence of tartaric acid. The formula suggested by Rai for the blue perchromate has been supported as without that the inclusion of tartrate ion in the composition of the blue perchromate cannot be explained.

Presence of any acid is essential in the preparation of the so-called blue peroxychromic acid or blue perchromate. Berthelot¹ observed that with different acids the colour of the compound formed varies. He noticed that whereas strong acids produce blue compound, the weaker acids like acetic and phosphoric give violet colour and still weaker like boric and hydrocyanic acids produce brown compound. Berthelot² also observed that with dilute chromic acid upto a temperature of 16°, the blue compound if at all formed is in traces and usually the brown colour predominates. Rai³ has observed the effect of alkali halides and salts of organic acids on the formation of blue perchromate. He has also observed that with acetic acid the blue perchromate formed is different from the one formed with sulphuric acid.

In the present paper the blue perchromate has been prepared in presence of tartaric acid. This acid has been selected due to two main reasons. Firstly it is practically insoluble in ether⁴ and secondly that the tartrate ion is a good complex forming anion. The blue perchromate thus formed has been studied with a view to arrive at a definite conclusion regarding the constitution of the blue perchromate regarding which there are several different views^{5,6,7}.

EXPERIMENTAL

The blue perchromate was prepared by mixing the ice cold solutions of 5% $K_2Cr_2O_7$

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†Present address:—Department of Chemistry, Govt. Science College, Gwalior (M.P.)

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(50 ml.), 20 vol. H_2O_2 (varying quantities) and tartaric acid (varying quantities). The blue perchromate formed was extracted with ethyl ether (100 ml). Tartaric acid was added shortly before the addition of hydrogen peroxide to avoid any interaction between potassium dichromate and tartaric acid. After separating the blue perchromate with the aid of a separating funnel, it was washed several times with ice-cold water to remove any possibility of tartaric acid or any other product going along with the blue perchromate. It was then transferred in a previously dried and cooled Erlenmeyer flask, corked tightly and placed in the refrigerator to freeze out water. After about 3 hours the blue perchromate was decanted in another dried and cooled Erlenmeyer flask and kept in ice.

Various studies were then made in the following manner:—

1. 5ml. each of this blue perchromate was allowed to decompose in four Erlenmeyer flasks (100 ml.), to which about 15 ml. of distilled water was previously added.

2. The blue perchromate was titrated iodometrically in two stages as suggested by Rai⁸ in the following manner:—

First Stage: The blue perchromate (5 ml.) was added to a neutral potassium iodide solution and the liberated iodine was titrated against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution ($N/82.4$) using starch as indicator. At this stage the colour of the solution was yellow and not green. *Second Stage:* On the completion of the first stage, to the same reaction mixture, $2N$ sulphuric acid was added and the further quantity of liberated iodine was titrated to the green end point against the same thiosulphate solution.

Similar studies were made with another blue perchromate prepared with sulphuric acid but the thiosulphate solution used in this case was $N/41.2$.

TABLE I

5% Potassium dichromate solution = 50 ml., $2N$ Sulphuric acid = 5 ml., 20 Vol. Hydrogen peroxide = varying quantities, Ethyl ether = 100 ml., Strength of Sodium thiosulphate solution = $N/41.2$.

Vol. in ml. of H_2O_2 added	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate used in titrating the blue perchromate			Water decom- position product	Ratios		
	First Stage	Second Stage			$\frac{b+c}{d}$	$\frac{c}{d}$	$\frac{b}{c}$
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	
5	3.50	5.70	4.00	2.30	1.42	0.61	
5	3.60	5.50	4.10	2.21	1.34	0.65	
10	7.40	11.60	8.90	2.19	1.30	0.63	
10	11.10	17.00	13.85	2.12	1.20	0.65	
20	12.00	21.80	16.00	2.25	1.36	0.55	
20	21.20	32.60	25.00	2.04	1.30	0.65	
30	13.70	21.90	16.10	2.08	1.36	0.62	
30	14.00	22.35	16.50	2.07	1.35	0.62	

TABLE II

5% Potassium dichromate solution = 50 ml, 2*N*. Sulphuric acid = varying quantities, 20 Vol. Hydrogen peroxide = 10 ml. Ethyl ether = 100 ml, Strength of thiosulphate solution = *N*/41.2.

Vol. in ml. of H ₂ SO ₄ added.	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate used in titrating the blue perchromate	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate used in titrating the blue perchromate	Water decomposition product.	$\frac{b+c}{d}$	Ratios $\frac{e}{d}$	$\frac{b}{c}$
a	First stage	Second stage	d	e	f	g
5	8.00	14.50	11.00	2.04	1.31	0.55
5	7.60	13.50	10.30	2.04	1.31	0.56
10	8.50	16.00	12.00	2.04	1.33	0.53
10	9.00	17.00	12.50	2.08	1.36	0.53
15	7.95	15.00	11.00	2.08	1.36	0.53
15	8.45	14.00	11.00	2.04	1.27	0.60
20	10.35	16.80	13.45	2.01	1.25	0.61
20	12.00	20.00	15.40	2.07	1.30	0.60

TABLE III

5% Potassium dichromate solution = 50 ml, 2*N*. Tartaric acid solution = 50 ml, 20 Vol. Hydrogen peroxide = varying quantities, Ethyl ether = 100 ml, Strength of thio-sulphate solution = *N*/82.4.

Vol. in ml. of H ₂ O ₂ added.	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate solution used in titrating blue perchromate.	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate solution used in titrating blue perchromate.	Water decom- position product	$\frac{b+c}{d}$	Ratios $\frac{e}{d}$	$\frac{b}{c}$
a	First stage	Second stage	d	e	f	g
10	1.60	1.60	1.70	1.88	0.94	1.00
10	1.60	1.60	1.70	1.88	0.94	1.00
20	1.70	1.70	1.70	1.94	1.00	1.00
20	1.70	1.70	1.70	1.94	1.00	1.00
30	2.30	2.40	1.90	2.47	1.26	0.95
30	2.30	2.40	1.90	2.47	1.26	0.95
40	3.20	4.90	3.60	2.13	1.28	0.65
50	3.30	5.10	3.60	2.33	1.41	0.63
50	3.30	5.10	3.60	2.33	1.41	0.63

TABLE IV

5% Potassium dichromate solution = 50 ml. 2*N*. Tartaric acid solution = varying quantities, 20 Vol. H₂ hydrogen peroxide = 10 ml., Ethyl ether = 100 ml, Strength of thio-sulphate solution = *N*/82.4.

Vol. in ml. of Tartaric acid added.	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate solution used in titrating blue perchromate.	Vol. in ml. of thiosulphate solution used in titrating blue perchromate.	Water decom- position product.	$\frac{b+c}{d}$	Ratios $\frac{e}{d}$	$\frac{b}{c}$
a	First stage	Second stage	d	e	f	g
10	2.40	3.80	3.20	1.93	1.18	0.63
10	2.40	3.80	3.20	1.93	1.18	0.63
20	1.50	2.40	2.00	1.95	1.20	0.62
30	2.10	2.00	2.50	1.64	0.80	1.05
40	1.70	1.70	2.00	1.70	0.85	1.00
40	1.70	1.70	2.00	1.70	0.85	1.00
50	1.60	1.60	1.70	1.88	0.94	1.00
50	1.60	1.60	1.70	1.88	0.94	1.00
75	1.40	1.40	1.20	2.33	1.16	1.00
75	1.40	1.40	1.20	2.33	1.16	1.00
100	0.90	0.90	1.10	1.64	0.81	1.00
100	0.90	0.90	1.10	1.64	0.81	1.00

DISCUSSION

R. Schwarz and Giese (loc. cit.) and Rai (loc. cit.) assigned CrO_5 and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$ formula respectively for the blue compound. Observations of tables I and II agree with those of Rai. The blue perchromate studies in the present case (Table III and IV) is the one prepared in presence of tartaric acid. The various ratios for this sample are different from those in tables I and II. It seems that along with H^+ ion, tartrate ion has also played some role in the formation of compound. Tartrate ion has been detected qualitatively in its decomposition products. Being practically insoluble in ether tartrate ion can not go through it. Moreover several washings with ice-cold water still minimise this possibility. In spite of this if it goes through ether it will get oxidised by the blue perchromate. The presence of tartrate ions in decomposition product thus confirms the possibility of its coming after forming a part of this blue perchromate.

Hexavalent chromium in CrO_5 cannot accommodate tartrate ion as beside valency, tartrate ion and peroxidic oxygen will then be placed in vicinity and in such a position the former may be oxidised. Moreover CrO_5 being a neutral molecule if associated with tartrate ion (henceforth written as T^{--}) will go in ether along with some cation (K, H or Cr^{--} in present case). If it goes as a salt of chromium(III), then there is no difference in the opinion of the above two workers except that instead of CrO_5 , Rai has taken Cr_2O_{10} anion. It can not go with K^+ as potassium perchromate is formed at a much lower temperature⁹, and that Cr^{+3} has been confirmed in its decomposition products¹⁰⁻¹¹. Its acidic character is not supported by pH studies¹².

The trivalent chromium in $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$ on the other hand can easily be expected to accommodate T^{--} ion leaving peroxy ion on hexavalent chromium. As suggested by Rai¹³ simultaneous oxidation and reduction of Cr_2O_7 ion takes place during the formation of blue perchromate resulting $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--}$ and Cr^{+3} which then combine to give $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$, the blue perchromate. In the present case Cr(III) is to accommodate $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--}$ and T^{--} . The remarkable low concentration of blue perchromate in the present case suggests a struggle between T^{--} and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--}$ to get preference from Cr^{+3} which is available in a limited amount due to the possibility of its being used up in the formation of chromium tartrate.

On the basis of above arguments, complexes like $(\text{CrT})_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}$, $\text{Cr}_2\text{T}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$ and/or $(\text{CrT})_2\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ seem to be formed in the following way:

1. Oxidation of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--}$: $3\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 + 9\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow 3\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--} + 6\text{H}^+ + 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

2. Reduction of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{--}$ to Cr_2O_3 : $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O} + 6\text{O}$.

—from the first reaction combine with Cr_2O_3 of the 2nd reaction to give Cr^{+3} as: $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 + 6\text{H}^+ \longrightarrow 2\text{Cr}^{+3} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

3. Formation of chromium tartrate: $2\text{Cr}^{+3} + 3\text{T}^{--} \longrightarrow \text{Cr}_2(\text{T})_3$.

4. Oxidation of tartaric acid by blue perchromate: $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}^{--} \longrightarrow \text{Cr}^{+6}\text{O}_7^{--} + 3\text{O}$.

and

tartaric acid + O $\longrightarrow$ Dihydroxy fumaric acid + H_2O .

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The dihydroxy fumaric acid can still be oxidised to the ultimate products Co_2 and H_2O .

5. Some of the tartrate ion take entry in the composition of the blue compound during its formation giving complexes as:—

and/or

Following may be the probable structural formulae for the above complexes:

For $\text{Cr}_2\text{T}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_2$:

For $(\text{CrT})_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10}$:

For $(\text{CrT})_3\text{Cr}(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$:

Complex formation in the aforesaid manner seems to have changed the mode of decomposition of the blue compound. In conformity with the observations noted in tables III and IV, the decomposition now seem to be as:—

and in water

which in presence of acid

Similar results can be obtained with second and third complexes also except that in these cases 8 and 9 oxygen atoms will evolve respectively in both the stages i.e. first and second and also after the treatment of water decomposition product with acid. The ratio $\frac{b+c}{d}$ in the cases will, therefore, be 6 : 3, 12 : 6 and 18 : 9 i.e. 2 : 1 which is in agreement

with the values obtained in tables III and IV column 'e'. Variations of ratios in column 'g' of the above tables from 0.62-1.65 show that with the varying quantities of the reactants, the nature of the blue compound changes from the one prepared in presence of H_2SO_4 (tables I and II) to the one having tartaric acid. The ratio of nearly 1:1 in column 'f' of tables III and IV show that the products of second stage and that of water decomposition product are same.

In every column of tables III and IV there are certain values which occur constantly in tables I and II. It indicates that if tartaric acid is less than 30 ml. or H_2O_2 more than 30 ml., tartrate ions do not enter in the composition of the blue perchromate. A definite quantity of both, i.e. H_2O_2 and tartaric acid is thus necessary to make the entry of tartrate ion a success.

The formula for the blue perchromate should therefore be $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_3$ and not CrO_5 .

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF SAUGAR,
SAGAR (M.P.)

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